

THE INTERPLAY OF COMPOSITE DEGRADATION MECHANISMS FOR LONG LIFETIME AIRCRAFT OPERATION

K. Grigoriou^{1*}, R. Ladani¹, P. Marzocca¹, A.C. Orifici¹, A. Khatibi¹, R. Das¹,
A.P. Mouritz¹ and C. Wright²

¹ School of Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia,

² Aerospace Division, Defence Science and Technology Group, Melbourne, Australia.

* Corresponding author (Katherine.Grigoriou@rmit.edu.au)

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Abstract

During operational service, aircraft structures are typically exposed to extreme temperature cycles, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, moisture, fatigue loading and potential impact damage. Environmental exposure conditions such as moisture, temperature and UV radiation can adversely affect the mechanical properties of composite materials. This study reviews the current knowledge on the individual degradation mechanisms and aims to develop an understanding of the interplay of composite degradation mechanisms under aircraft in-service loading conditions and long lifetimes.

1 Introduction

Composite materials have been increasingly used in aerospace and other advanced applications due to their improved specific strength and stiffness and superior resistance to corrosion and fatigue, compared to metals. However, the long lifetimes associated with military assets mean that much of the Australian Defence Force (ADF) aircraft fleet has composite materials only employed in tertiary (non-flight-critical) areas or under extremely conservative design conditions. Future aircraft are expected to see composite materials employed widely with increased optimisation, increasing their importance as part of the flight-critical, load bearing structural systems. Whilst the scientific community have extensive experience with flight-critical metallic structural systems, there is comparatively less experience with in-service behaviour of flight-critical composite structures.

During operational service, aircraft structures are typically exposed to extreme temperature cycles, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, moisture, fatigue loading and potential impact damage. Environmental exposure conditions such as moisture, temperature and UV radiation can adversely affect the mechanical properties of composite materials. Aircraft structures are usually coated with a UV resistant paint and hence any UV damage is usually restricted to the topmost layers of the structure [1]. Moisture diffusion can often lead to plasticisation of the polymer matrix and hydrolysis resulting in a reduction in the elastic modulus, strength and glass transition temperature of the composite [2]. Combined exposure to temperature and moisture can cause swelling, inducing residual stresses and microcracks.

Airframe structures are also susceptible to impact threats from a wide range of sources including bird strikes, hailstones, tools dropped by maintenance personnel, service vehicle collisions and foreign objects. Impact incidents can result in immediate degradation in the load-bearing capability of the structure but also affect the long-term durability. Damage to the internal structure, which may be difficult to detect, can continue to grow under repeated fatigue cycles and environmental exposure [3].

Although a large body of knowledge is available on the different damage mechanisms, the extent to which they are relevant to aircraft in-service operational conditions over long periods of time and their relative importance to flight-critical structures remains unclear. Further, the criticality of the synergy between damage mechanisms under in-service loading, environmental exposure and long lifetimes is

still unknown, and the interactions of loading and damage that require further study have not been clearly identified.

This study reviews the current knowledge on the individual degradation mechanisms and aims to develop an understanding of the interplay of composite degradation mechanisms under aircraft in-service loading conditions and long lifetimes. Section 2 reviews hygrothermal ageing, and the subsequent sections review the interplay of hygrothermal ageing with UV radiation (Section 3) and impact (Section 4).

2 Hygrothermal Ageing

Aircraft components are frequently exposed to atmospheric moisture, rain and accumulated (trapped) water. Composite airframe components will absorb moisture given the correct hygrothermal conditions. Moisture uptake can degrade the mechanical properties of composite laminates, particularly at elevated temperatures.

Hygrothermal aging induced damage to the composite is difficult to research since real-time aging may require several years or even decades before insightful changes to the mechanical properties become noticeable. As such, majority of experimental research studies use artificial aging methods, typically involving accelerated aging of composites using either (i) environmental chambers under controlled temperature and humidity levels or (ii) immersing the composites in water at higher than ambient temperature. Hygrothermal aging can be viewed as a coupling between polymer matrix degradation due to moisture absorption with heat.

Several studies have reported that moisture uptake in composite increases with relative humidity and temperature. For instance, Tual et al. [4] investigated the effects of temperature on moisture uptake rate in carbon-epoxy composite immersed in water for up to 7500 h or 312 days where the moisture uptake rate was accelerated at higher temperatures. However, at prolonged periods of exposure, the moisture absorption tends towards an equilibrium value. Irrespective of the exposure temperature, the maximum water saturation level attained by the composites was similar at ~1% by weight. Furthermore, the authors reported that the size (thickness and surface area) of the laminate had no influence on the moisture uptake rate or maximum saturation levels. The results of this study show that the maximum moisture saturation level in a laminate is inversely proportional to fibre volume content. The laminates manufactured using resin infusion or pre-preg consolidation containing ~55-58% fibre volume fraction absorbed less moisture, ~0.8% moisture by weight. Whereas, the laminate containing 48% fibre volume fraction when manufactured using resin transfer molding showed a greater moisture uptake of ~1.3%. This finding can be attributed to the polymer's affinity to moisture absorption being greater than for the fibre reinforcements. The presence of carbon fibre reinforcements affect the total moisture absorption in a composite laminate. This raises an important question on the effects of fibre or ply orientation in a laminate towards the moisture absorption behaviour of composites. Very few studies have investigated this effect, which reported that the ply orientation in a laminate has a weak influence on the moisture uptake rate and the full saturation levels [6-8].

The kinetics of moisture and water ingress into polymers relate invariably to the molecular structure of polymers and the chemical kinetics that characterise water affinity to the polymer molecules [9]. In thermoset polymers such as an epoxy, molecular topological factors, such as nano-voids provide free volume access routes to permit water ingress. Free volumes in thermosets depend on the extent of crosslinking and the final molecular conformations and polymer microstructures [10]. The free volume only affects the initial stages of water diffusion in polymer, suggesting an absorption-based response to moisture transport in bulk polymers.

The diffusion of water in thermoset polymers can be predicted by the Fickian diffusion model [10]. However, the mechanism of moisture ingress in composite laminates is more complex due to the microstructural arrangements of the fibre and matrix phase. The swelling of the matrix phase from

moisture absorption promotes microcracking and debonding at the fibre-matrix interface [4, 11]. Thus, in composite laminates the presence of fibre reinforcement affects the moisture absorption through mechanisms like capillarity or transport in microcracks related to fibre-matrix debonding [5, 12]. Due to the presence of such mechanisms, the Fickian diffusion model is less reliable for predicting the water uptake in composites [13-15].

Studies [4, 5, 7, 16-26] have reported moisture saturation level of ~0.75% to 2% by weight for carbon fibre-epoxy composites exposed to 100% relative humidity (i.e. water immersion test) and a range of temperatures. These saturation values represent the most extreme case of moisture uptake in composites. However, a composite airframe will experience varying weather condition with a cyclical change in relative humidity and temperatures. Whilst most studies in the literature reported the use of water immersion tests or a combination of constant relative humidity and temperature exposure, very few studies have reported the use of environmental conditioning of composite that is representative of the cyclical weather condition experienced by an airframe [15]. Patel and Case [19] investigated the effect of altering the exposure condition between flight (120°C at 0% RH for 90 min) and storage (30°C at 85% RH for 24 h) for 500 cycles, which were chosen as a representative exposure condition for composite components in an aircraft engine. The authors reported that the moisture uptake for the composite was 0.49% after 500 cycles, which is significantly lower than the maximum saturation levels reported in other studies. However, it is difficult to achieve realistic exposure conditions using laboratory tests. The environmental conditions experienced by an airframe during service vary significantly. Its simplification to cyclic variation in humidity and temperature using environmental chambers may not truly represent the exposure conditions. To address this issue, aircraft manufacturers and operators have conducted studies focused on comparative assessments of flight and ground-based environmental exposure effects on composite coupons.

The first extensive study [27], a 10 year worldwide ground exposure at outdoor sites was structured to supplement data obtained through service evaluation of B737 spoilers, DC-10 rudders and L-1011 fairings. The following exposure locations were included: NASA Langley, VA; San Diego, CA; Honolulu, HI; Frankfurt, Germany; Wellington New Zealand; and Sao Paulo, Brazil. The moisture absorption for materials exposed at sites in Wellington, New Zealand and Sao Paulo, Brazil, where average annual humidity is ~75-80%, were consistently higher than California which experiences dry weather conditions. Although, the moisture absorption values are location and material dependent, their saturation value which is attained at ~5 year period, range between ~0.7% to 2%. This range of moisture saturation level is very similar to the data for the laboratory based immersion tests reported in ref [4, 5, 7, 16-26]

In a subsequent study [28] conducted by Boeing and NASA, a 10 year ground and flight exposure, was structured to compare (i) ground and flight exposure data and (ii) the effects of solar versus non solar exposure. For the flight exposure tests, composite coupons were installed on top and bottom surfaces of B737 flap-track fairing tail cones and in the non-pressurized interior of the aircraft behind the aft pressure bulkhead. The moisture absorption results for the ground-rack exposed coupons were marginally higher than flight exposed coupons. Similar trends were also observed for data after 1, 2, 3 and 10 year of exposure.

Moisture absorption can detrimentally affect the mechanical performance of composites [4, 6, 26]. The results in ref [4, 6, 26] show degradation in tensile strength with increasing moisture content. The effect of moisture on the longitudinal tensile strength is less severe with less than ~10% reduction at a range of moisture content values. Whereas, the reduction in the transverse tensile strength is more severe, which reduces by ~20% at ~0.8% moisture content. With an increase in moisture content beyond 1%, the transverse tensile strength degrades even further to less than 50% of the strength for dry composite material. Similarly, these studies reported that the moisture uptake did not affect the longitudinal elastic modulus of the composite, but a marginal reduction in the transverse modulus was measured for moisture saturated composites.

The longitudinal tensile strength is a fibre dominated property, and thus it remains largely unaffected by the moisture induced interfacial debonding or the matrix softening. However, under compressive load, an early onset of fibre kinking induced failure of the composite has been reported due to the matrix softening induced by moisture absorption [26]. As a result, a greater reduction in the longitudinal compression strength has been reported for moisture saturated composites in comparison to the dry composite [6, 7, 26]. Moisture absorption induces swelling of the matrix which has detrimental effect on the fibre-matrix interface bond. The swelling of the matrix causes considerable relative shear deformation at the interface between fibre and matrix, resulting in the debonding of the interface [11]. This does not affect the elastic modulus which is considered a bulk property for a composite containing a set volume of matter as a continuum. On the contrary, when loading perpendicular to fibre direction, the debonding or weakened interfaces will affect the elastic modulus, since it will disrupt the solid state continuum that contributes to this bulk material property. Thus, the transverse elastic modulus is affected by the interfacial debonding resulting from the moisture absorption. In addition, the interfacial debonding of the fibre-matrix interface has a detrimental effect on the interlaminar properties of the laminate. The results in ref [4, 6] show a reduction to the interlaminar shear strength of ~10-35% for composites with moisture absorption of ~0.7-1%. However, the modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite largely remains unaffected or in some systems increases slightly due to the moisture absorption [5, 17, 25, 26]. These studies attributed the increase in toughness to the moisture induced plasticisation of the epoxy which promotes plastic deformation of the thermoset as opposed to the usual brittle-like failure, and thereby increases the fracture toughness of the epoxy.

The mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites are known to degrade with increasing temperature. The rate of this degradation is more severe as the temperature approaches the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the matrix. Studies [36, 42, 43] have shown that the shear and compression properties are reduced significantly under Elevated Temperature Wet (ETW) conditions, with a 40% reduction in shear strength and a 20% reduction in open hole compression strength at 50°C. As these properties are largely dominated by the matrix stiffness, as the resin softened and weakened due to the increasing temperature and moisture content, the strength reduced significantly. The tensile properties remained relatively unaffected.

3 Interplay of UV Radiation and Hygrothermal Ageing

When exposed to UV radiation, chemical degradation of the resins occur resulting in chain scission and crosslinking. Eventually, these chemical reactions will result in the microcracking and chalking on the exposed surface. During the condensation cycle, resin hydrolysis and moisture absorption occur but the resin erosion is significantly less severe [29].

Microcracks which have developed on the surface following UV exposure, provides pathways for rapid ingress of moisture. The presence of moisture can also enhance photo-oxidation reactions resulting in further chain scission and chain crosslinking. Any soluble products or particles on the surface can be removed by the condensation [29]. Then a fresh polymer surface is exposed to the following UV cycle and more damage is subsequently created by UV followed by the subsequent cleaning of the surface damage by water in the next condensation cycle.

Barbosa et al. [30] conducted a study on carbon-epoxy composites exposed to alternative cycles of UV radiation (340 nm, 0.89 W/m² at 80°C) for 8 hours and water condensation at 50°C for 4 hours in an accelerated aging chamber. This cycle was repeated for 2160 hours and resulted in a 0.58% weight loss, degradation of the fibre/matrix interface and exposure of the carbon fibres on the exposed surface. The exposure also caused a 7°C decrease in the glass transition temperature, which was attributed to chain scission, which increased chain mobility. Similar findings have been observed in other studies, following moisture absorption [5, 16, 31, 32].

Kumar et al. [2] conducted a study investigating the effect of sequential exposure to UV radiation followed by condensation, and cyclic exposure to both UV radiation and condensation on a carbon

fibre/epoxy laminate. These results were compared to specimens exposed to only UV radiation or only condensation. For the sequential exposure to UV radiation followed by condensation, the specimens were first exposed to UV radiation in the 295-265 nm band at a temperature of 60°C and an irradiance level of 0.68 W/m² for either 250 or 500 hours. After UV exposure the specimens were exposed to water vapor condensation at 50°C and 100% RH for either 250 or 500 hours. For the cyclic exposure to both UV radiation and condensation, the specimens were exposed to alternating cycles of 6 hours of UV radiation followed by 6 hours of condensation, for a total of 500 hours or 1000 hours. When the composite specimens underwent sequential exposure of UV radiation followed by condensation, the specimens initially lost weight during the UV radiation cycle and subsequently gained weight during the condensation cycle. These results were expected and in accordance with the weight changes observed during exposure to only UV radiation, or only condensation. Surface morphology confirmed these findings, with surface characteristics that were a combination of the two individual exposure conditions [2]. The top surface showed little degradation, however the edges showed microcracking and erosion of the epoxy matrix. When the specimens underwent cyclic exposure to both UV radiation and condensation, the change in weight was unexpected. The specimens showed a slight increase in weight up to 125 hours of exposure, before showing a steady decrease for the remainder of the test. An average weight decrease of 1.25% was recorded after 1000 hours of cyclic exposure [2]. Surface morphology showed severe physical degradation in the form of extensive matrix erosion, void formation and fibre-matrix interface debonding. Cyclic exposure caused the epoxy rich layer on the surface to erode, revealing the underlying carbon fibres and causing fibre loss and extensive microcracking.

Exposure to UV radiation results in the formation of a thin layer of chemically altered epoxy on the laminate surface. Subsequent water condensation then removes any soluble UV degradation products, which exposes a fresh layer that can once again be attacked by UV radiation [33]. This process then repeats leading to significant erosion of the epoxy matrix. Moisture ingress into the epoxy matrix also increases the availability of OH- and H+ ions, which increases chain scission and crosslinking, causing matrix embrittlement.

Kumar et al. [2] also conducted uniaxial testing to determine the effect of degradation by UV radiation and condensation on the mechanical properties. No significant reduction in longitudinal or transverse modulus and the longitudinal strength was recorded for specimens exposed to both UV radiation and condensation, either sequentially or cyclically. It's expected that over longer periods of environmental exposure, the synergism between UV and condensation can cause significant matrix erosion that load transfer ability between fibres may be compromised, leading to a deterioration of fibre-dominated properties. The transverse tensile strength was severely degraded. Specimens exposed to sequential exposure of 1000 hours of UV radiation followed by 1000 hours of condensation exhibited a decrease of 21% in transverse tensile strength, which was a similar decrease to specimens exposed to only condensation for 500 hours. This reduction was most likely due to irreversible hydrolysis and plasticisation of the epoxy matrix due to moisture absorption as well as the presence of surface microcracks induced by UV radiation exposure. Degradation was most severe for specimens exposed to cyclic UV radiation and condensation. The transverse tensile strength was reduced by 29% following 1000 hours of exposure [2].

Nakamura et al. [33] expanded on this work to evaluate the combined effects of environmental condition and cyclic fatigue loading. The specimens were exposed to the same environmental conditions and fatigued for 100,000 cycles. After mechanical fatigue the specimens were subjected to three-point bend tests to measure the change in flexural modulus, which proved to be greater for specimens subjected to environmental degradation and higher amplitudes of cyclic loading. The flexural strength was reported in terms of the critical maximum moment per unit thickness. Results showed that further weakening of specimens due to mechanical fatigue was less pronounced when it was already weakened by environmental degradation. Specimens subjected to combined mechanical fatigue and exposure to UV radiation and condensation showed a 11% decrease in flexural modulus and 15% decrease in failure moment compared to undegraded specimens under the same fatigue load [33]. It is important to note, however, that only 2 samples per test condition were used. The small number of specimens in each condition limits the statistical relevance of the data.

The aforementioned studies have focused on unpainted composite laminates. In the study [28] conducted by Boeing and NASA painted composite coupons were installed on the top and bottom surfaces of B737 flap-track fairing tail cones and in the non-pressurized interior of the aircraft behind the aft pressure bulkhead to assess the effect of UV radiation. The moisture absorption results were similar for both the UV irradiated and unexposed samples for up to 10 years of exposure, indicating that moisture uptake is independent of UV exposure on a painted carbon epoxy specimen. Residual strength results showed that the samples exposed to both moisture and solar radiation maintained the same strength values as samples that were not exposed to solar radiation [27, 28]. However, when exposed to both UV radiation and moisture under accelerated ageing conditions, both painted and unpainted carbon epoxy laminates have been shown to lose mass, with the unpainted samples losing ~33% more mass due to the synergistic effect of UV radiation and moisture, described above [41]. The unpainted samples however retained the same residual strength as the painted samples for up to 1000 hours. However, although the paint provides protection initially, the underlying composite substrate is eventually degraded with extended exposure duration.

4 Interplay of Impact and Hygrothermal Ageing

A major issue in the use of composites on aircraft structures is associated with the occurrence of delamination or interlaminar cracks, which can be induced by in service impact. Due to the degradation of mechanical properties after hygrothermal aging, as described above, the impact resistance can be significantly influenced. The matrix cracking and fibre matrix interfacial debonding due to long term exposure to moisture reduces the impact resistance of the composite. Although few studies have looked at the impact response of aged composites, many of the studies draw unified conclusions.

When testing at ambient temperatures, moisture does not significantly affect the damage initiation energy and impact energy dissipation process at low velocity impact. Mokhtar [34] studied the effect of hygrothermal aging at 70°C, 85%RH for up to 2100 hours on the impact response of a CFRP, and found that the extent of damage due to impact was not greatly influenced by moisture. However, at elevated temperature, the presence of moisture has a significant effect on damage initiation energy. Karasek et al. [35] evaluated the influence of temperature and moisture on the impact resistance of carbon/epoxy laminates. It was found that only at elevated temperatures, moisture had a significant effect on damage initiation energy and the energy required to initiate damage was reduced with increasing temperature.

The toughness, G_{IC} of carbon fiber epoxy composites is expected to increase with increasing moisture content, however is independent of soak temperature. Toughness values of the carbon fibre epoxy increased with increasing moisture over the entire range of saturation, with a maximum increase of ~64% and scatter of ~6% [25,26]. The mode II toughness, G_{IIC} decreases with increasing moisture content due to the degradation of the fibre-matrix bonding. With increasing moisture content, the fibres are able to move without deforming the matrix, which has softened due to moisture absorption [25,26].

Compression strength after impact and moisture exposure studies have been inconclusive. When moisture was absorbed, carbon fibre epoxy laminates showed larger damage areas, however the measurements of the damage areas showed larger scatter [25,26]. Specimens which were impacted with an energy of 6 J/mm showed a 52% decrease in compression strength, compared to undamaged specimens which were reduced by 17% due to the moisture absorption alone. It is believed that moisture softens the matrix and hence the stiffness is reduced. As a result, there is less resistance to fiber kinking and the laminates can fail at lower stresses. Callus [36] found that moisture exposure at elevated temperature caused reductions of ~15% in open hole compression strength and strain to failure. Saito [37] found that compression after impact of CFRP laminates were hardly affected by moisture absorption. Similar results have been recorded in [20, 17, 38], with some studies showing a positive effect on impact behavior after hygrothermal aging.

The aforementioned studies have predominantly focused on low velocity impact and fewer studies have looked at high velocity impact. Liu [39] found that due to the weakened fibre matrix interface, delamination failure severity increased with aging time and impact velocity. Wosu [40] found that the compression strength, elastic modulus and energy absorption decreased exponentially with moisture and temperature, and the combined effect on the damage process was more apparent than when acting alone. Temperature has a stronger effect on the compression after impact strength, more so than either the maximum impact load or the damaged area especially when the aging temperature nears the glass transition temperature.

5 Synthesis

Analysis of the current body of knowledge indicates that moisture, and hygrothermal ageing conditions are most critical for fibre reinforced polymer composites over long exposure times. This may be exceptionally true for aircraft structures exposed to extreme temperatures, where the moisture uptake rate can be significantly increased and the T_g reduced. The synergistic effect of hygrothermal aging and UV radiation exposure can have detrimental effects due to its unique matrix erosion mechanism, where the irradiated surface can be washed away by moisture allowing deeper penetration of environmental damage. However, it has been indicated that if the surface is painted, the substrate is protected from UV radiation damage. In this case, although moisture ingress is still possible, material loss is prevented. Although some initial research has been undertaken on the interplay of different mechanisms, further analysis is required to improve the understanding of synergistic effects experienced by aerospace structures in order to improve the current design lifetimes.

Table 1. Summary of the effects of damage mechanisms on a carbon epoxy laminate.

<i>Damage Mechanism</i>	<i>Environmental Effect</i>	<i>Residual Strength Reduction</i>	<i>Key References</i>
Moisture	0.8 – 1.2% moisture saturation level	Tensile [0.90] Shear [0.80] Compression [0.80]	4, 6, 27, 28
UV Radiation + Moisture	0.8 – 1.0% moisture saturation level	Compression [0.80] Shear [0.80]	27, 28
Impact + Moisture	1.4% moisture saturation level	OHC [0.85] CAI [1.0]	36, 37, 42
Moisture + Temperature	1.4% moisture saturation level	@ 50°C Shear [0.60] Tensile [0.90] OHC [0.80]	36, 42, 43

6 Conclusion

This paper explores the current knowledge on individual damage mechanisms of hygrothermal aging, UV radiation and impact, and begins to develop an understanding of the interplay between these mechanisms under aircraft in-service loading conditions. Although a large body of knowledge is available on the different damage mechanisms, the extent to which they are relevant to aircraft in-service operational conditions over long periods of time and their relative importance to flight-critical structures remains unclear. Further, the criticality of the synergy between damage mechanisms under in-service loading, environmental exposure and long lifetimes is still unknown. Although some initial research has been undertaken on the interplay of different mechanisms, further analysis is required to improve the understanding of synergistic effects, including those due to cyclic fatigue loading, experienced by aerospace structures in order to improve the current design lifetime.

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